

**METHODS OF IMPROVING SPEAKING COMPETENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH
TO B2 LEVEL LEARNERS.**

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Annotatsiya Ushbu maqolada maktablarda ingliz tili darslarida axborot texnologiyalari va interfaol usullarning ahamiyati, shuningdek., B2 talabalariga ingliz tilini o'rgatishda nutq kompetensiyasini oshirish yo'llari haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ingliz tili, interfaol usullar, nuqta kompetensiyasi, axborot texnologiyalari, tilshunoslik, til.

Abstract. This article provides information about the importance of information technology and interactive methods in English language classes in schools, as well as ways to improve speaking competence in teaching English to B2 students.

Keywords: English language, interactive methods, point competence, information technologies, linguistics, language.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена информация о важности информационных технологий и интерактивных методов на уроках английского языка в школах, а также о способах повышения разговорной компетентности при преподавании английского языка студентам уровня B2.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, интерактивные методы, балльная компетентность, информационные технологии, лингвистика, язык.

Introduction:

Today, improving the outdated education system of our country, which is on the path of independent development, and learning and teaching foreign languages, along with all developed and developing countries, has become the need of the hour in our country, Uzbekistan. It is no exaggeration to say that the conditions created for young people and all our compatriots to learn foreign languages are proving their positive results. Serious changes and updates are taking place not only in the case of foreign languages, but also in all aspects of the world of science. Of course, at the beginning of such huge creative works lies the spirit of our country's leader, attention to the youth, confidence in the future. An example of this is the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 610 of August 11, 2017 "On measures to further improve the quality of teaching foreign languages in educational institutions". Language is the main means of communication, without which it is difficult to imagine the existence and development of human society. Today, at a time when there are great changes in social relations in our world, communication media (information technologies) require the improvement of students' communicative skills, they can exchange ideas in different situations during interaction with other participants of communication, language and so It is necessary to use the norms of behavior correctly. In such conditions, the main goal of a foreign language is the formation of communicative abilities, that is, interpersonal and intercultural communication in a foreign language is required. A number of didactic problems can be solved using the Internet in English classes: reading skills and competencies using global network materials forming; improving the writing ability of schoolchildren; filling students' vocabulary; formation of students' motivation to learn English. In addition, this work aims to explore the possibilities of Internet technologies to expand the horizons of schoolchildren, establish and maintain business relations and contacts

with peers in English-speaking countries. Students can take part in online tests, quizzes, contests, olympiads, correspond with their peers in other countries, chat, videoconference, etc.

Materials and Methods:

In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important component of professional education. People learn such knowledge first at school, college, lyceum, and then at institutes, training courses, or independently by getting acquainted with the basic information sets that help to learn a foreign language. Today, there are large collections of educational materials for people with different levels of language skills. Success in achieving this goal depends on the practical methods and skills of teachers. The ability to use information technologies and modern teaching methods helps to quickly understand new materials. By combining different methods, the teacher is able to solve specific educational programs. In this regard, teachers and students should familiarize themselves with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, the ability to choose the most effective methods to achieve one's goals is formed. The use of several methods of teaching and learning will give effective results. Teaching is carried out in small steps and is based on the student's existing knowledge system. As time progresses, innovations in every field are increasing. Different styles are also emerging in language teaching. A step-by-step approach to teaching English based on the learner's potential, level, and age gives good results. In this case, students are divided into groups based on teaching at the primary level, teaching at the middle level, and teaching at the higher level. A special program is developed by the teacher for each stage. The use of modern pedagogical technologies in teaching English in schools has a good effect. Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It is also intended to increase the quality of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning English. The role of modern technologies in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of CDs, audio books, and picture annotations in English language classes improves speech and helps to speak fluently. The most useful method in language teaching is mutual oral conversation. Communicating more in class encourages you to learn words faster. Reading more fairy-tale books, memorizing poems in English will make your speech more fluent, and watching cartoons in English will also encourage you to pronounce English words correctly. For this reason, the main thing in learning a language is listening and repeating. It's just that organizing methods according to the topic depends on the teacher's dexterity, experience, and in which case what methods are used.

Currently, communication, interactivity, authenticity of communication, language learning in cultural context, autonomy and humanitarianism of education are given priority. These principles allow the development of intercultural competence as a component of communicative competence. The ultimate goal of teaching foreign languages is to teach a free orientation in a foreign language environment and the ability to adequately respond to different situations, i.e. contact Today, new methods using Internet resources are opposed to traditional foreign language teaching. To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real, real-life situations that stimulate the learning of the material and develop adequate behavior (that is, the so-called principle of communication authenticity). New technologies, especially the Internet, are trying to correct this error.

Communicative approach is a strategy that simulates communication aimed at conscious understanding of the material and methods of working with it, creating psychological and linguistic preparation for communication. It is not particularly difficult for the user to implement a

communicative approach on the Internet. A communicative task should invite students to discuss a problem or question, students not only exchange information, but also evaluate it. The main criterion that allows distinguishing this approach from other types of educational activities is that students independently choose linguistic units to form their thoughts. In the communicative approach, the use of the Internet is very well encouraged: its purpose is to interest students in learning a foreign language by accumulating and expanding their knowledge and experience.

One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources is interaction in the lesson. is to create a mystery, which is usually called interactivity in the methodology. Interactivity is "combining, coordinating, and complementing communicative goals and resulting efforts by means of speech."

By teaching the real language, the Internet helps to build speaking skills and abilities, and also ensures genuine interest and therefore effectiveness in teaching vocabulary and grammar. Interactivity not only creates real situations from life, but also forces students to respond appropriately to them in a foreign language. One of the technologies that provides student-oriented education is the project method as a method of developing creativity, knowledge activity and independence. The typology of projects is diverse. Projects can be divided into monoprosjects, collective, oral, concrete, written and Internet projects. In actual practice, it is often necessary to deal with research projects, mixed projects with creative, practice-oriented and informational features. Project work is a multifaceted approach to language learning, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method helps to develop active independent thinking of students and directs them to joint research work. In my opinion, project-based learning teaches children to cooperate, and learning to cooperate instills moral values such as mutual aid and empathy, builds creativity and activates students. In general, the inseparability of teaching and education is observed in the project teaching process. The project method develops students' ability to communicate, culture of behavior, the ability to form ideas concisely and easily, to tolerate the opinions of communication partners, and the ability to obtain information from various sources. processes using modern computer technologies, creates a language environment that contributes to the emergence of natural needs. in communication in a foreign language.

Results and Discussions:

The importance of speaking competence in teaching English to B2 students cannot be overemphasized. As the main component of language learning, speaking competence plays an important role in improving the ability of B2 level students to communicate, understand and master English effectively. This basic skill is essential for academic success, social interaction, and future career opportunities. In this context, speaking competence serves as a basis for developing common language skills and educating confident, articulate individuals who are able to thrive in a globalized world. In this discussion, we examine the multifaceted importance of speaking competence as it relates to teaching English to B2 learners, its transformative effects on language acquisition, and its implications in education and beyond. We emphasize the wider influence outside.

Speaking competence plays an important role in teaching English to B2 students because it directly affects their ability to communicate effectively in the language.

Here are some key points about the importance of speaking competence in teaching English:

1. Communication skills: The development of speech competence allows students at the B2 level to express their thoughts clearly and fluently, and develops communication skills both academically and in real life.

2. Language fluency: Fluency in speaking facilitates language fluency, allows students to express their thoughts and ideas with confidence, thereby increasing their overall language skills.

3. Academic Achievement: Strong speaking competence contributes to academic success by enabling students to express their ideas coherently, participate in discussions, and understand learning material more effectively.

4. Social interaction: Effective speaking skills are essential for B2 level students to engage in social interactions inside and outside the classroom, to develop meaningful connections and cultural exchange.

5. Career opportunities: In a globalized world, speaking English opens up a variety of career opportunities and becomes an important skill for the future success of B2 students.

6. Building confidence: Developing speaking competence in B2 level students instills confidence, encourages active participation in classroom activities and positive attitude towards language learning.

7. Engaging and motivating: An engaging and lively classroom environment is often provided by teachers with strong speaking skills. Their expressive delivery and effective use of voice modulation can increase students' interest and motivation in learning English.

8. Cultural Awareness: Through proper pronunciation and speaking, teachers can convey the cultural nuances and context embedded in the English language. It promotes a deeper understanding and appreciation of English-speaking cultures.

9. Building Confidence: Hearing a teacher speak clearly and confidently can inspire students to develop confidence in their speaking skills. This creates a positive language learning environment where students are encouraged to express themselves in English.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, speaking competence is an integral part of English language teaching because it significantly affects students' language acquisition, comprehension and confidence. Teachers with strong speaking skills not only provide linguistic guidance, but also foster the supportive and engaging environment necessary for effective language learning. Kompyuterlar va boshqa qurilmalardan foydalanish butun ta'lim jarayonining muvaffaqiyatini belgilaydi. Sufficient attention should be paid to the formation of speech skills and the development of social flexibility in the training conducted during the educational process. In addition, the success of each lesson in education largely depends on the correct organization of the training. The lesson should be based on the creative cooperation of the teacher and the student. Only then will students be able to think independently and will be educated.

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